

DEVELOPMENT OF BIOBASED FOAM FROM JATROPHA SEED OIL POLYOL: EFFECT OF ISOCYANATE ON SOME PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF THE BIOBASED FOAM

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ABSTRACT

Designers and manufacturers need to study the appropriate factors that affect the polyurethane foams production and full usage in order to exploit their full potential because of the continuous growth of their usage. This work studied the effectiveness of Toluene Isocyanate (TDI) on the tensile strengths, compression set value, elongation at break, density support factor and the hardness of the biobased polyurethane foam. The chemicals (Polyol, Dimethyl ethyl amine, Silicone oil, Methylene chloride, Tin catalyst and Water) were weighed in separate containers and added into the mixing vessel. Various levels of TDI were added last and immediately followed mixing. The results showed that the, density, porosity index and tensile properties of the foam densities of the samples increase with increase in TDI concentration. The samples that had TDI concentration of 10ml showed the best result. In all the foam samples with TDI concentration of 10ml showed better properties than the commercial standard. The tensile properties such as elongation at break and tensile strength vary with increase in TDI concentration. The results established showed that X-Americana oil can be used to produce good flexible polyurethane foams.

Keyword: TDI, biobased foam, Jatropha seed oil, polyol

1 INTRODUCTION

Polyurethanes has numerous applications such as aeronautics, automobile, building construction, marine, and many household applications [1]. Due to their light weight and stiff structure, their usage continues to grow in many areas [2]. Since PU's are among the widely used construction materials which can be formulated for medical devices [2, 3], designers and manufacturers need to study the significant factors that affect their production and full usage in order to leverage these versatile properties. Polyurethane foam (PUF) is the most widely used as flexible foam plastic. It is used to produce a wide variety of items including thermal insulation and packaging materials, comfort cushions, bed mattresses, carpet backings and resilient floor coverings [4]. polyurethane foams have a high degree of versatility due to the many ways they can be applied in the production of a wide range of materials which are used differently in domestic and industrial applications. Its production involves the step-growth polymerization of a polyiso-cyanate of functionality 2.7 with a polyalcohol (polyol) of molecular weights from 2000 to 10000 and functionality 2 to 3, followed by the blowing reaction of two parts polyiso-cyanate with one-part water in the presence of an amine and tin compound catalysts and other additives. Toluene diisocyanate

(TDI) and polyalcohols are the basic ingredients for the production of polyurethane foam. In the preparation of biobased PUF, diisocyanate must be used. Isocyanate is a functional group with formula $R-N=C=O$. Organic compounds that contain an isocyanate groups are referred to as isocyanates. An isocyanate that has two isocyanate groups is known as a di-isocyanate. Di-isocyanates are manufactured for reactions with polyols in the production of polyurethanes as a class of polymers. Toluene diisocyanate (TDI) and diphenyl methane diisocyanate (MDI) are two most common aromatic isocyanates that are used in polyurethane manufacturing. Isocyanate is a compound that is very reactive. Its reactions can be grouped into two types; polymerization and reactions with active hydrogen compounds. When reacted with polyol it attacks the oxygen compounds of the hydroxyl groups [5] to produce a urethane linkage. The other reaction of isocyanates is the reaction with amines to form urea. The influence of the isocyanate in the properties of the polyurethane, produced using soy oil polyol has been also studied. The properties of the polyurethane strongly depend on crosslinking density and the structure of isocyanate. Thus, the density, support factor, compression and tensile strength were obtained for aromatic triisocyanate; while, aliphatic isocyanates gave rubbery materials with the highest elongation at break and swelling. As the synthesis of isocyanates is more complex than that of polyols, chemists tend to use commercially available isocyanates and design new polyols to tune the properties of the final material. Common diisocyanates used in the synthesis of polyurethanes are 4,4'-methylene-bis (phenylisocyanate) (MDI), 2,4-toluene diisocyanate (TDI), isophorone diisocyanate (IPDI), 4,4'-dicyclohexylmethane diisocyanate, hexamethylene diisocyanate (e), and lysine methylester diisocyanate (LDI) [6]. Therefore, this experiment set out to investigate the effect of TDI on some physico-chemical properties of biobased foam obtained from the reaction of TDI and polyol derived from *Jatropha* seed oil.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

Materials used for this particular research were obtained from the commercial market. NIMA FOAM manufacturing company Yola, Nigeria, were the chief suppliers of most the product including (Toluene-di-isocyanate, Dimethyl ethyl amine, Silicone Oil and Methylene chloride and stannous octate) while *Jatropha* seed oil polyol was synthesized here in the laboratory.

2.2 Method

The chemicals (Polyol, Dimethyl ethyl amine, Silicone oil, Methylene chloride, Tin catalyst and Water) were weighed in separate containers and added as shown in (Table 1) into the mixing vessel. Various levels of TDI were added last and immediately followed mixing. After adequate mixing, the mixture was quickly poured into the prepared mould, allowed to rise undisturbed and left to cure over night before removal from the mould [7].

2.3 Experimental design

The experimental formulation for the various level of TDI in the formulation of biobased polyurethane foam is presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Experimental formulations of biobased PU foam for various levels of TDI solution

Materials (ml)	Industrial formulation (grams)	formulation A	formulation B	formulation C	formulation D	formulation E
Polyol	100	12	12	12	12	12
TDI	57	2	4	8	10	12
WATER	5	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08	0.08
AMINE	0.12	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.02
SILICONE	1.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
METHYLENE CHLORIDE	1.02	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.04
STANNOUES OCTATE	0.28	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06	0.06

2.4 Characterization of Biobased Foam

2.4.1 Support Factor/Hardness Test

The indentation hardness test was carried out in an indentation machine (Hampden mechanical Tester). The test specimens of dimension 0.15cm*0.15cm*0.20cm were positioned on a support plate, so that the center of the specimens was located below the center of the indenter (diameter = 0.35cm). The support plate was perforated to allow for free flow of air. A force of 5N was applied to the test area and the thicknesses of the test-piece measured. The specimens were indented at rate of 100mm/min. to produce an indentation of 75% indentation (25% thickness of the original test sample), the applied force was released. This loading and unloading were repeated two times more and immediately after the third unloading the specimens were indented to 40% of their thicknesses. Each time, the deflection was maintained for a period of 30 seconds and the corresponding forces in Newtons were displayed on the monitor which were noted and recorded as the indentation hardness index.

2.4.2 Density Test of the Foam Sample

Three test-pieces each were each tested using weighing balance capable of weighing to an accuracy of 0.01g, the values were initially in grams and were also converted then to kilo grams and their respective values recorded. The dimensions of the test-pieces were measured using meter rule in centimeter and were converted to meters. Each sample weighs were the divided by their respective volume calculated.

2.5.3 Compressibility (compression set) Test

The compressibility (compression set) test was carried out using a compression device. The test specimen was cut according to ASTM-D 3574 standard dimension of 0.5cm*0.5cm*0.25cm. All test-pieces were kept free of any contamination and skin on the vertical sides. It is noteworthy, that as long as the original sample thickness is less than the sample length and width, compression set is independent of sample thickness. Each test sample was placed the compression device which consists of two flat plates having dimensions larger than those of the test-pieces. The provided spacers and clamps were arranged such that the plates were held parallel to each other and space between the plates was adjusted to the required deflected height. The test-pieces were compressed to 75% of their original thickness and maintained under constant condition for 22 hours. Then, each test-piece was removed from the apparatus and was placed on a wood.

2.5.4 Tension (Tensile Strength) Test

Three samples each for the test were die-cut into “dumb-bell” shape. The thickness, width and gauge length of each test piece was measured at five evenly distributed points on the test-piece and the average found. The test-pieces were placed in the grips of the testing machine and care was taken to ensure that the test-pieces were symmetrically positioned so that tension is distributed uniformly over the cross section. The machine was then turned on after which maximum force and the distance between the inside edges of the two reference lines were measured immediately prior to the break of the test-pieces. The maximum forces and elongation results were monitored from the monitor screen and recorded. As shown in plate 1. The final elongation at break and tensile strengths were calculated using the standard equations.

Plate 1. effect of load on pu foam

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Results of Physical Tests

Physical tests such as density, compression set and indentation force deflection (IFD), were carried out on samples of foam produced. The results of the tests were presented by a graphical representation for each test.

3.1.1 Effect of TDI concentration on the density of X-americana biobased Pu foam

The effect of the of the concentration of TDI on the biobased foam formulation is presented in the graph below Figure 1. As can be seen from the Figure 2, the density of the biobased foams increases initially with increase in TDI concentration in water (in-situ blowing agent). As more TDI is added, the foam density increases up to 8ml of TD inclusion after which it began to drop. This development can be explained as follows; at the initial stage of the graph, the molecular weight of the TDI/polyol copolymer increases with increase in TDI concentration a corresponding increase in crosslinking density of the biobased foam. This increase in crosslink density led to a decrease in the cell volume of the foam thereby giving rise to the observed increase in density of the foam with increase in TDI addition [8]. As more and more TDI is added, the crosslink density of the copolymer (foam) approaches optimal and hence the gradual decrease in foam density observed in the second regime of this experiment. However, further addition of TDI to the TDI/polyol copolymer led to polymer dissociation (fragmentation) giving rise to smaller molecule or oligomers with the expected low crosslink density, hence the decrease in density observed after the optimal addition of TDI in this experiment [9].

Figure 1. Effect of TDI on foam density

3.1.2 Effect of TDI on support factor of biobased foam

From Figure 2. it was observed that, the support factor increased slightly with an increase in TDI concentration, then dropped sharply before a rise again. To explain this, initially the increase in the TDI concentration might have been responsible for the decreased in the porosity of the cells formed during the reaction thereby increasing the density of foam which implies that the support factor would also increase [9]. But in the second phase the sharp decline in the support factor may be caused by a collapse of the foam cells, which may be due to the irregular bonding (urea precipitation) that occurred as the TDI concentration increased. This collapse led to the sharp drop in the support factor of the biobased foam in question. Later a slight increase was noticed which may be due to the infusion of air bubbles into the cells as TDI concentration is further increased.

Figure 2. Effect of TDI on the support factor of the biobased foam

3.1.3 Effect of TDI on hardness of biobased foam

The Figure 3. showed an increase in hardness with increased TDI concentration. From the figure it can be observed that the hardness increased as TDI increased in concentration. Then it began to decrease

as the TDI concentration increased to a level where any increment in TDI concentration had no effect on the hardness of the biobased foam. The initial increase of the hardness was due to the increment in the TDI which led to water increase [10], which causes an increase in foam density. These leads to the increase in foam hardness [11]. in the second phase of the graph, the hardness of the foam decreases. These may be due to burning of the core caused by the vaporization heat. reduction in the auxiliary blowing agent (kept constants during experiment also leads to a decrease in the foam density and its hardness. The vaporization heat may be reduced by increasing the concentration of amine (kept constant during experiment) in the formulation [12].

Figure 3. Effect of TDI on the hardness of biobased foam.

3.1.4 Effect of TDI on tensile strength of biobased foam

Figure 4. illustrates the tensile properties of the biobased foams. As can be seen, initially the tensile strength increased with increase in TDI concentration, and then it begins to drop with an increase in TDI concentration above 8.0 ml. The increase in tensile strength of the biobased foam may be due to the increase in the molecular weight of the foam [12]. The decrease in tensile strength with increase in TDI concentration is due to the more porous structures formed with increased blowing agent concentration, which is brought about by the reaction of excess TDI with the moisture of the biobased-polyol used. The extra porous structures resulted from increase in concentration of in-situ blowing agent. These porous structures are bound to affect the cross- linking density by decreasing it. Since the cross-link density in biobased foams play a major role in their strengths, it is no wonder that the tensile strength decreased with decrease in density.

Figure 4. Effect of TDI concentrations on the tensile strength of foam

3.1.5 Effect of TDI on Elongation at break of biobased foam

Figure 5. above shows a rise in elongation as the TDI concentration increases, once it reaches its optimum point the elongation at break began to drop significantly. Initially the rise in elongation might be caused by the increase in molecular weight of the copolymer leading to a stronger crosslinking between cells, but an increase in TDI index may have caused the sudden drop in the elongation property of the foam. One of the properties that distinguishes a good foam from a bad foam is its percentage of elongation which describes its elastic properties [11]. Figure 1.4 shows that the elastic property of the foam was maintained between normal ranges of 148-154 KN/m² up till the point where the TDI concentration reaches 8.0ml. Thereafter a sharp drop in elasticity property was experienced. The result indicates that the elongation at break fell within the range given by ASTM D-3574 that a good foam should have minimum value of 150%.

Figure 5. Effect of TDI concentrations on elongation at break of biobased foam.

3.1.6 Effect of TDI on compression set values of biobased foam

The compressive strength of the biobased foam increased slightly and then decreased to 2.4 with an increase in TDI concentration. The mixing ratio of the polyols TDI may be responsible at this point. A sharp increase was observed as the concentration of TDI is further increased. This may be due to the density

of the foam and the inner structure, especially cross-linkage in the foam. A higher cross-linking degree is necessary to keep the strength of the structure [13]. However, from Figure 6. all foam samples produced fell within the ASTM D-3574 set standard range of 1-10% (NIS 295:1993) for compression tests of polyurethane foams.

Figure 6. Effect of TDI on the compression set values of foam.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Polyurethane foams were produced from x. Americana seed oil polyol, using different concentrations of TDI. The experimental physical result tests showed that, 8.0ml concentration of TDI gave optimal values and this is comparable to the results of the control sample. Therefore, the result of this study has established that X. Americana oil can be used to produce good flexible polyurethane foams.

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